

Breakout session

Leveraging different types of molecular data to understand biology of health and disease

Description of the breakout session

Health-RI is building a data infrastructure. The current focus is on clinical patient data, medical imaging as well as on the molecular (“omics”) data which are the subject of this break-out session. Omics data is becoming very prominent in the study and diagnosis of very diverse diseases, from rare diseases to cancer, and they are important for the understanding of common diseases but also for personalizing treatments. Different types of molecular data look at different types of molecules of life and combining these is the holy grail for understanding the biology of life and health. In this session we want to hear the motivation for sharing molecular data from our experts and engage panel members as well as the audience in discussions about the technical and social barriers that need to be cleared by and through Health-RI to make it work.

- The premise: understanding biology is fundamental to understanding health and multi-omics research is needed to understand biology.
- The Health-RI connection: We need services like metadata agreements, catalogues, and secure processing environments to find, access and re-use multi-omics data in a safe way.
- Building the story: How is Health-RI infrastructure going to advance your research and contribute to the understanding of the molecular processes in life?

Speakers:

- X-omics: Prof. dr. Peter-Bram 't Hoen, Chair of Bioinformatics, Radboudumc
- Proteomics: Dr. Magnus Palmblad, Associate professor/group leader bioinformatics, LUMC

- Genomics: Prof. dr. Lisenka Vissers, professor of Translational Genomics, Radboudumc
 - Metabolomics: Dr. Denise Slenter, postdoc in Translational Omics, Maastricht University
- Session Chair:
- Prof. dr. Bauke Ylstra, Amsterdam UMC

Format of the breakout session

The session was opened by Bauke Ylstra and this was followed by 4 brief presentations by speakers from different omics areas. After that a moderated discussion with the audience took place about the role of data infrastructure in multi-omics research.

The slides can be found at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14287992>

Summary and outcomes of the discussion

During the session we saw examples of a lot of data, and many suitable tools to work with that data. However, a lot of the data is dispersed, and many of the tools are used by small working groups and there is not a lot of knowledge outside on how these can be applied.

If we want to promote the re-use of data then prospective re-users need to get trust in the data and get to know the tools that are available already to work with the data. This holds for any level of “opening up” of the data to a larger audience: first from the primary care into research, then from research into a national research community, and finally from the national to the international community. To facilitate this trust, we need to establish quality criteria, consisting of 4 points:

- Quality control metrics for both the process of data collection and the data itself
- Openness of the data: as open as possible, as restricted as necessary
- Standards-compliance: the different omics types each have international organisations dealing with setting standards: Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), Proteomics standards initiative (PSI) and metabolomics standards initiative (MSI)
- Metadata: there must be sufficient metadata to unambiguously document the data, it needs to be correct and machine actionable. In short, the data must be FAIR.

To facilitate omics research, we need a single “interoperable database”. This is not a problem that we can solve nationally; we will need to connect to the international initiatives as standard setting organisations, international databases, and international research infrastructures.

We need to keep an eye on the variety of omics data: in the session we had presentations from genomics, proteomics and metabolomics, but in the audience we also had a representation from microbiomics, and exposomics researchers are keeping an eye on our progress.

What Health-RI can do

There are several challenges on the path where Health-RI collaboration can make a difference.

Societal aspects

- Health-RI can play a role in the proper and homogeneous processes surrounding the consent of the patients and other data subjects.
- Health-RI can play a role in establishing and keeping the trust of the data subjects; it is important to give them insight in how the data is being used and what benefits this has for society.
- Health-RI can play a role in generating the trust of the data collectors: data holders will need to invest their time in making the data available, and they will need to get a (scientific/career) recognition for that effort.

Legal aspects

- Health-RI can work on the proper legal frameworks facilitating data sharing
- Health-RI already has done work on changing laws on using the BSN for data linkage

Technical aspects

- Health-RI can coordinate efforts to set up the national infrastructure for storing and processing large volumes of omics data. However, note that health-RI will not be “buying” the hardware needed to do this.
- Health-RI can work on improving the machine actionability of the available (meta)data
- Health-RI can help develop the tools that allow data collectors to prevent “losing the metadata”, so that the process of onboarding data sets in the infrastructure is facilitated.

Knowledge dissemination and capacity building

- Health-RI needs to make sure that users as well as producers of data are sufficiently aware of the tools and data that are available.
- Health-RI can raise awareness with researchers about the need for adopting metadata standards

Challenges: closing the gaps and creating trust!

Slide: Lisenka Vissers

Organisers of the break-out session

- Rob Hooft (Health-RI Architecture team)
- Janet Vos (Health-RI International team)
- Celia van Gelder (Health-RI Life Sciences team, International team)